

The impact of safety protocols implemented to seafarers arriving in Manila

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Abstract

Due to the pandemic, traveling became more complicated than before because of the protocols the travelers must comply with. This paper identified the impact of safety protocols being implemented among seafarers who were arriving in Manila. It specifically aimed to identify the impact in terms of the seafarers' mode transportation, health, time for work, and income as well. The researchers conducted an online survey among 100 seafarers who arrived in Manila; and identified how they are affected by the implemented safety protocols. It was revealed that the seafarers experienced difficulty in boarding ships as well as a decrease in the number of workers. Travel speed is greatly affected, although it provides a positive impact on their health as the seafarers are confident that they have a higher chance of not contracting the virus. Similarly, their mental health is in good condition because of the safety that the protocols provided them; and in turn, affects their time management and that their time for works affected as well. Thus, they have more time with their families than they have before the pandemic. The respondents' salary was also affected. Since there is a notable impact in this study, it suggested that those who are applying for a job in the cruise industry must have sufficient knowledge about the company they intend to gain employment, and they must be physically and mentally ready as it is more challenging than it was before the pandemic.

Keywords: *Safety protocols; seafarers; Manila; cruise industry.*

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Introduction

The tourism industry has created detailed protocols for the functioning of all types of tourism enterprises or facilities. The protocols are in line with the guidelines and protocols provided by government departments, and they will be reviewed as needed on an ongoing basis. The impact of the new normal on people's health explains how the health sector will adapt to the new normal. To stop the spread of this deadly disease, societies have halted most economic activities, allowing only the most important activities, such as those connected to food and health, to continue.

Previous studies have indicated that human mobility and patterns of interaction play a direct impact in infectious disease transmission, particularly during pandemic (Arthur et al., 2017; Buckee et al., 2021; Sabin et al., 2020). As a corollary, travel during pandemics is generally prohibited. Various governments have recommended or adopted a variety of control and preventive measures to halt the spread of the virus and 'flatten the curve,' depending on the specific governance, socioeconomic conditions, and cultural environment. Based on recent studies, working from home and reducing consumption, minimizing community contacts, and limiting abroad travel are all effective mitigation strategies. Meanwhile, as the concern of the researchers implies, the tourism industry's response to this will be discussed since travel or traveling is one of the most common scenarios that could occur in this industry. One of the most affected are the seafarers coming and going out to have a vacation or to attend to their work.

The hassle that it could bring them is in such a high percentage due to the fact that they are coming from outside the country of their destination that could possibly be the epicenter of the virus, or if they are travelling. Seafarers would still have to observe protocols, specifically if the country of destination implements stricter quarantine guidelines.

The safety protocol is the independent variable in this study, whereas seafarers' transportation, health, time for work, and income are the dependent variables. Safety protocols could have a direct impact on seafarers' transportation, health, time for work and income. The researchers were able to identify that the independent factor will decide what the dependent variable must do and that the dependent variables will be subject to any changes based on the independent variables' responses. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly impacted the maritime transport sector, creating a disruption to the industry (Oyenuga, 2021). The seafarers' health has been in critical condition due to the pandemic, their unfavorable work condition eventually led them to experience physical and psychological issues (Yuen et al., 2018). In this research, it attempted to identify the impact of the safety protocols to the seafarers that have arrived in Manila.

In our field of specialization, this research will be helpful because there are only a few studies that are related to this paper due to the fact that the pandemic just began in 2020 which directly affected the tourism industry specifically in the travel and accommodation industry. Said industries constitute the main topic of this study. It is important for students to understand the possible impact of the safety protocols in traveling. To add up, this study would aim to understand the positive and negative impact of the COVID-19 protocols. Solutions are also suggested which would lead to an increased awareness about the importance of certain restrictions.

Related Studies

The literature review describes aspects related to the study on the effects of safety protocols to seafarers. The travel community has fought for equal access to health care in the past. IATF Resolution No. 119 s. 2021, which was modified, prescribed suggestions that must control the global tour that enters the country of all completely vaccinated people who have been vaccinated within the Philippines. IATF Resolution No. 123-C s. 2021, issued June 28, 2021, sets out guidelines for international entry for all fully vaccinated persons in the Philippines (IATF Resolution No. 128A s. 2021). Persons who have traveled and have been vaccinated abroad and have only stayed in "green" countries/jurisdictions in the last 14 days immediately prior to arrival-the jurisdictions of "green" countries / Ministry of Health (DOH) risk countries are categorized. As "low" based on the fixed incidence that occurs.

During the pandemic, everyone seeks ways to avoid being infected by the COVID-19 virus. From a top-down level, this includes social distancing and other social alterations to ensure that the virus may not infect people within the communities. However, the above principles alone are not effective enough, as people who are not routinely protected from the virus are more likely to be infected on a daily basis in order to maximize safety. These safeguards include wearing mask upon going out, avoiding touching facial areas such as eyes, nose, and mouth with hands, and at least 20 seconds with soap (recommended) or alcohol (alternative). Washing hands regularly for a second and taking appropriate safeguards such as respiratory hygiene and cough labels are strongly encouraged (WHO, 2020; Sharma, 2020).

According to Okeleke and Aponjolonsun (2020), the pandemic has caused a major impact to Nigerian shipping transportation, specifically the movements of ships and cargo; this is due to the temporary closure of ports and docks. Maritime transportation suffered a big loss as sea ports were restricted and closed. Due to such impact, many were affected such as the travelers by sea and seafarers and crew per se. The pandemic had also caused the loss of workers at ports as some of them decided to temporarily stop working or resigned due to their fear of contracting the virus, and by that, ports had been unable to operate more effectively and efficiently.

The implemented border restrictions as imposed on the local and state ports has slowed down or even eliminated the chances of crew to have their shore leave. International transportation was greatly affected, especially the maritime transportation, due to the said border closure, which eventually caused the crews or seafarers to experience more difficulties especially on their mental health. The restrictions were ordered for the safety of the country or the local community, however, it is an undeniable fact that it has affected the seafarers as well or even the travelers, especially when those ships are for transportation purposes such as cargos or just to carry passengers (Shan, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

This study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents according to gender and age?
2. How did the safety protocols affect the seafarers in terms of transportation, health, time for work, and income?

Significance of the Study

This research will aid in the development of a precise and reliable understanding of the impact of safety protocols on travel during the Covid-19 pandemic. As a result, this will be extremely beneficial to the following:

Students of Hospitality Management. Hospitality Management students can use the results of this study as a guide to understand the significance of adhering to safety protocols when traveling during a pandemic. The safety protocols can assist hospitality management students in determining what they will do to prevent further infection and spread of the virus.

Seafarers. The positive and negative effects of these safety protocols can assist seafarers in determining what they should and should not do.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study focused on the safety protocols in traveling during pandemic in the Philippines. This study was conducted during the school year 2021-2022. The subjects are the people in the Philippines who travel to other countries. According to the total of the 2019 survey on seafarers, between April and September 2019 was estimated at 2.2 million. The total of 2021 survey on overseas Filipino workers (OFW) this pandemic till May 2021 is at estimated 1.2 million. The world is facing unparalleled global health, economic and social health. Travel is the most affected by this pandemic. Safety health protocol and updating travel restrictions in every country applied for this global health pandemic. Seafarers are the people in the Philippines who travel to other countries that we focus on. The research focused on how safety protocols affect seafarers when they travel to other countries, which served as our foundation.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative approach and descriptive research design, which measures the impact of safety protocols to seafarers during pandemic. A total of 100 seafarers were surveyed using simple random sampling.

Sampling Procedures

The researchers employed random sampling that would be the technique utilized in selected samples from the population. This sampling technique is the best and easiest way to choose samples especially when having a large population. It also gives everyone a chance of being selected. The participants would be the seafarers who are arriving in Manila and would take the 15-item questionnaire.

Instruments

Research questionnaire was the main tool in the research. The type of questionnaire will be the Bipolar Likert Scale, in which the respondents' answers came from the given choices only which would range from agreeing to disagreeing. The questionnaire was validated, and reliability tested. The reliability test is 0.82 at Cronbach alpha. The first part of the questionnaire will be the demographic profile of the respondents followed by the questions about the impact of safety protocols implemented to seafarers arriving in Manila.

Data Collection

This study provides a process, or a particular point of view from the perspective of those involved, in the gathering of information among seafarers. A survey questionnaire was administered directly to the chosen sample of the study. After the instruments were validated, 100 copies of the questionnaires were given out successfully through an online survey. The survey was conducted online due to the protocols that restricted the researchers from conducting a personal contact survey. The quantitative research techniques using the options Agree or Disagree were used to investigate how the safety protocols affect the seafarers arriving in Manila. Following the completion of the questionnaires, the data was checked, analyzed, and interpreted. For question number 1 which is about demographic profile, the data were interpreted and analyzed using frequency distribution. For question number 2, data were interpreted and analyzed using the measure of central tendency, which is the mean, and is verbally interpreted as Agree or Disagree.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Frequency distribution of the respondents according to demographic profile (n=100)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	66	66%
	Female	34	34%
Age	22-25	52	52%
	26-30	32	32%
	31-35	9	9%
	36-40	7	7%

In Table 1, out of 100 respondents, 66 (66%) are males while 34 (34%) are females. The findings showed that the majority of the respondents are males. In terms of age, 52 (52%) are aged 20-25, 32 (32%) are aged 26-30, 9 (9%) are aged 31-35, while 7 (7%) are aged 36-40. The findings showed that the majority of the respondents are aged 20-25, followed by 26-30, then 31-35, lastly, 36-40.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of the respondents with regards to transportation

Questions in terms of Transportation	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The safety protocols cause difficulty in boarding the ship.	62	32	5	1	3.55	Strongly Agree
The safety protocols decreased the number of seafarers in the ship.	54	45	10	1	3.42	Strongly Agree
The safety protocols cause the cruise ships to reach their designated place slower.	56	35	10	1	3.48	Strongly Agree
As a seafarer, do you agree that safety protocols make your travel transportation faster?	37	27	28	8	2.93	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00: Strongly Agree, 2.51 – 3.25: Agree; 1.76 – 2.50: Disagree; 1.00 – 1.75: Strongly Disagree

Table 2 presents that the mean average for the first question “*The safety protocols cause difficulty in boarding the ship*” is 3.55 which means Strongly Agree. It means that the seafarers strongly agree that the safety protocols cause difficulties in boarding the ship.

For the second question, “*The safety protocols decreased the number of seafarers in the ship,*” the average mean is 3.42 which means Strongly Agree. For the third question, “*The safety protocols cause the cruise ships to reach their designated place at a slower pace,*” the average mean is 3.48 which means Strongly Agree. For the last question, “*As a seafarer, do you agree safety protocols make your travel transportation faster?*” the average mean is 2.93 which means Agree.

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents had either agreed or strongly agreed to the above-mentioned questions, which means that there is such a notable effect brought to them by the implemented safety protocols in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, in terms of transportation. However, there are a few who disagreed or strongly disagreed to the particular item.

Table 3. Frequency distribution of the respondents with regards to health

Questions in terms of Health	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The safety protocols help you reduce the risk of having the virus.	68	30	2	0	3.66	Strongly Agree
The implementation of safety protocols has been more effective in reducing the spread of the virus.	63	34	0	3	3.57	Strongly Agree
The safety protocols help your mental health more especially with the fear of getting a virus.	62	37	1	0	3.61	Strongly Agree
The safety protocols help reduce the chance of seafarers getting the virus.	60	36	4	0	3.56	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00: Strongly Agree, 2.51 – 3.25: Agree; 1.76 – 2.50: Disagree; 1.00 – 1.75: Strongly Disagree

Table 3 showed that the mean average for the first question, “*The safety protocols help you reduce the risk of having the virus*” is 3.66 which means Strongly Agree. For the second question, “*The implementation of safety protocols has been more effective in reducing the spread of the virus,*” the average mean is 3.57 which means Strongly Agree. For the third question, “*The safety protocols help your mental health more especially with the fear of getting a virus,*” the average mean is 3.61 which means Strongly Agree. For the last question, “*The safety protocols help reduce the chance of seafarers getting the virus,*” the average mean is 3.56 which means Agree.

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed to the above-mentioned questions, which means that there is such a notable effect brought to them by the implementation of the safety protocols in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, in terms of the health status of the respondents. However, there are a few who have disagreed or strongly disagreed to the indicated question.

Table 4. Frequency distribution of the respondents with regards to time for work

Questions in terms of Time for Work	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The safety protocols have helped you learn to manage time.	46	27	21	6	3.13	Agree
The safety protocols increased your working time.	56	32	12	0	3.44	Strongly Agree
The safety protocols decreased your working time.	34	26	32	12	2.86	Agree
The safety protocols affect your time management.	54	35	9	2	3.41	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00: Strongly Agree, 2.51 – 3.25: Agree; 1.76 – 2.50: Disagree; 1.00 – 1.75: Strongly Disagree

Table 2.2 showed that the mean average for the first question, “*The safety protocols have helped you learn to manage time*” is 3.13 which means Agree. For the second question, “*The safety protocols increased your working time,*” the average mean is 3.44 which means Strongly Agree. For the third question, “*The safety protocols decreased your working time,*” the average mean is 2.86 which means Agree. For the last question, “*The safety protocols affect your time management,*” the average mean is 3.41 which means Agree.

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed to the above-mentioned questions, which means that there is such a notable effect brought to them by the safety protocols in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, in terms of their time for work. However, there are a few who disagreed or strongly disagreed with the indicated question.

Table 5. Frequency distribution of the respondents with regards to salary

Questions in terms of Salary	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
As a seafarer, safety protocols cause you to spend more money.	49	37	14	0	3.35	Strongly Agree
To what extent do you agree that these safety protocols decreased your salary?	45	39	16	0	3.29	Strongly Agree
To what extent do you agree that these safety protocols increased your salary?	39	30	27	4	3.04	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00: Strongly Agree, 2.51 – 3.25: Agree; 1.76 – 2.50: Disagree; 1.00 – 1.75: Strongly Disagree

Table 5 showed that the mean average for the first question “*As a seafarer, safety protocols cause you to spend more money*” is 3.35 which means Strongly Agree. For the second question, “*To what extent do you agree that these safety protocols decreased your salary?*”, the average mean is 3.29 which means Strongly Agree. For the last question, “*To what extent do you agree that these safety protocols increased your salary?*”, the average mean is 3.04 which means Agree.

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed to the above-mentioned questions, which means that there is such a notable effect brought to them by the safety protocols in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, in terms of their Income. However, there are a few who disagreed or strongly disagreed.

Conclusion

The researchers concluded that the majority of the respondents were male, as it seems that the dominant gender working in this field are males. While in terms of age, the majority of the respondents are aged 20-25, as it seems that most of them are newly hired workers or perhaps freshly graduated from their respective courses. From the overall findings, researchers discovered that most seafarers have high positive perception in terms of transportation, health, time for work, and income.

The following recommendations are formulated based on the results of the study. This is addressed to the concerns listed on the significance of the study.

1. The researchers recommend that those who are trying to work in the seafaring field or those who are coming back must do research first about the company that they are looking forward to work at, especially that individual companies might have different ways of operation, benefits or incentives, which could be desirable for them.
2. It is important that the seafarers comply with the safety protocols no matter what, because in the first place it is for their safety and everyone who is onboard. It might seem a lesser need, especially during these months. Following the protocols will eliminate their chances of encountering a future problem regarding the matter.
3. The seafarers must adapt to the new way of their operation to reduce their risk of being stressed brought about by such changes caused by the safety protocols. They must also be able to understand that they are working amidst the pandemic thus, there are risks, despite how little the chance is, that they might be infected.
4. The seafarers should be wary of their physical and mental health as they work, in order for them to avoid further stress or exhaustion as they work in accordance with the safety protocols that are being implemented on their work.
5. The researchers recommend that the future researchers seek further details about the changes in terms of the safety protocols as it might vary for the years to come, or perhaps remain as what it is. They can study about such safety protocols for the general, for their safety in case they will do their future study amidst the pandemic.

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